

EFFECTIVENESS OF HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION SYSTEM ON HR FUNCTIONS OF THE BSNL, TAMILNADU CIRCLE

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Cite This Article: Dr. L. Manivannan & R. S. Jayasakthivel Rajkumar, "Effectiveness of Human Resource Information System on HR Functions of the BSNL, Tamilnadu Circle", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 87-91, 2017

Abstract:

The human resource management (HRM) is acknowledge-based economy. The idea, expertise, creative, and innovative workforce are necessary to meet the challenges in a knowledge-based economy. The human capital management is the complex process, but, an imperative for the organisation. Consequently, the several organisations use the human resource information systems (HRIS) gather, store and analyse the information for carrying out the human resource (HR) functions. The HRIS growth helps the HR practitioners understand the information technology and the information system as a part of the HR functions mainly to develop and use the best HRM programmes. Its implementation in the organization coupled with the sophisticated software executes the HR functions with the challenges that make the HR professionals taking an active part in and giving full cooperation to the organisation as the true strategic business partners. This study attempts to find out the HRIS effect, effectiveness, and impact on the HR functions with the top management, the HR managers and the HR executives employed in BSNL (Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited), Tamil Nadu Circle. Further, it shows that the HRIS has a direct significance to the HR functions and providing the HR professionals an opportunity to enhance their contribution to the firm.

Key Words: HRM (Human Resource Management) HRIS (Human Resource Information System) & HR Function

Introduction:

The latest technology, moulding the human management in the organisation, is a continuing challenge for the HR executives during the 21st century. It attracts, developing, and retaining the best human talent in the labour market. An effective HR management in a firm requires the prompt and right information on the current and potential employees in the labour market. The HR managers should have unawareness of the new changes in the technology to control over the human management not to increase only the employees 'quality information but also to have an effect on the overall organisation effectiveness. The human resource information system (HRIS) in the organisation reduces the routine and traditional HR activity. It combines the human resource management (HRM) with the information technology (IT). It acquires, storing, manipulating, analysing, retrieving, and distributing the information to execute the HR function. It is the database containing information to find out the skilled workers for the job execution in the HR department and integrating all the HR department service. It has undergone the basic process of the manual information-keeping systems into the computerized systems. Currently, it encompasses the payroll, the time and attendance, the appraisal performance, the administrative benefits, the management information system, the recruiting, the learning management, the training system, the performance record, the employee self-service, the scheduling, and the absence management.

Review of Literature:

Dr. Shikha N. Kheral and Ms. Karishma Gulati has investigated the benefits and role of the HRIS in the strategic activities by the HR managers of the IT companies. This study has selected the 127 respondents from the seven IT companies by the simple random sampling method to explore the overall HRIS contribution in the human resource planning. It has collected the data through the primary sources with the questionnaire construction. The data analysis has shown the highest mean of 3.02 that refers to the HRIS being the ability to manage the ample data and the lowest standard deviation of 0.766; the employees, a comprehensible about the HRIS ability to store the voluminous data. The human resource is an important asset for the IT companies to face the competitiveness. The HRIS is an excellent tool for the IT companies that have not absorbed the HRIS fully. Hence, the IT companies should need to work on the HRIS application. A few limitations of this study are the industry perspective and the interview of select respondents' biased view over the questionnaire.

This research paper has analysed the role of human resource management on the effective staff education improvement and the main indicators of organisational management such as the recruitment and selection, the design and implementation of the training programs, the employee performance evaluation, and the employees training in the organisational unit. It has selected the 120 respondents from the administrators and teachers by the simple random sampling. The tool of this study is the researcher-made questionnaire containing 40 questions. This paper has used the Likert-scale to analyse the collected data. To compare the result, it has

used the statistical model of one-sample t to analyse the each question related to the indicator of management of human resources. In addition, the study has compared the each item with an emphasis on organisational status by using t-model of the two independent groups. Finally, this paper has concluded that the impact of human resource management on the effective organizational improvement is the level of 1% alpha.

An organisation success depends upon the valuable human resource utilisation. Of late, the organisation treats the human resource as the strategic asset to achieve the sustained competitive advantage and outperforming the rivals. But, many challenging issues keep the organisation lagging behind to enjoy the technological benefits. This paper has tried to explore the hurdles based on the response of human resource (HR) executives from some companies operating in Bangladesh. It has found the management reluctance; the employee privacy issues, the organizational internal resistance, and the conversion cost that are the most potential issues to impede the HRIS implementation. Finally, it has suggested some measurable actions required to improve the technological execution in some companies of Bangladesh.

Bal, Y., S. Bozkurt and E. Ertemsir (2013) have described the HR function as a process involved in the matters relating to the HR in an organisation. Besides, the HRIS performs all the Human Resource Administrative functions. It assists the organisation to manage all the HR information such as leave, skills inventory, performance evaluation, training and development and others. Consequently, many HR functions had some degree of automation applied to gain the effectiveness on the user satisfaction.

Objective of the Study: There are several studies on the HRIS application in the Indian organisations. But, a few studies on the HRIS importance are available in India. The main aim of this study is to analyse the effect, effectiveness, and impact of the HRIS on the HR department of the BSNL.

Methodology: The researcher has used the quantitative approach to collect the data. He has received the permission from the authorities concerned after explaining to them about the purpose of the study. The participants of this study are the HR employees implementing the HRIS in their organisation. It is a study based on the self-administered questionnaire with the top management, the managers, and the executives working in the HR Department of the BSNL. The researcher has assured the respondents not to show their identity to anyone. He has collected, tabulated and analysed the data using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and described the findings of this study using proportions and percentages.

Results and Discussions:

Gender strength in BSNL: The following Table 1 shows the number of male and female employees working in the HR department of the BSNL.

Table 1: Number of male and female employees in BSNL

S.No	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	80	72.73%
2	Female	30	27.27%
	Total	110	100.00%

Table1 shows the select male and female respondents working in the BSNL. Out of 110 respondents, the 72.73% respondents are male and the 27.27%, female.

Age of Respondents: The following Table 2 shows the select age-group of male and female respondents working in the BSNL.

Table 2: Age wise male and female respondents

S.No	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	18-22	23	21.15%
2	23-27	17	15.38%
3	28-32	15	13.47%
4	33-37	28	25.00%
5	38-42	08	07.69%
6	43-47	11	09.62%
7	48 and above	08	07.69%
	Total	110	100.00%

Table 2 shows the select age-group of male and female employees employed in the BSNL. Out of 110 respondents, 21.15% are between the age group of 18–22; 15.38 %, 23–27; 13.4 7%, 28–32; 25%, 33–37; 7.69%, 38–42; 9.62%, 43–47; and 7.69%, above 48 years of age.

Educational Qualification of Respondents: The following Table 3 shows educational qualification of the respondents of this study.

Table 3: Educational qualification of the respondents

S.No	Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
1	Under graduate	28	25.00%
2	Post graduate	78	71.15%
3	Doctoral degree	04	03.85%

	Total	110	100.00%
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Out of the 110 participants, the 71.15% of the respondents are the post graduates; the 25%, the undergraduates; and the 3.85%, the doctoral degree.

Length of Service of Respondents: The following Table 4 shows the respondents total experience in their respective jobs in the BHEL.

Table 4: Length of the service of the respondents

S.No	Respondents	Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1	74	00-12	74	67.30%
2	23	13-20	23	21.14%
3	13	21-25	13	11.53%
	Total		110	100.00%

Table 4 shows the respondents experience in their service of the BSNL. Out of the 110 respondents, the 67.30% of the respondents, who are a part of the study, are working between 0–12 years; the 21.14%, 13–20 years; and the 11.53%, 21–25 years.

Designation of the Respondents: The following Table 5 shows the select respondents designation in this study

Table 5: Designation of the respondents

S.No	Respondents	Designation	Frequency	Percentage
1	13	Top Management	13	11.53%
2	08	Sr. Manager	08	07.69%
3	21	Manager	21	19.23%
4	68	HR executives	68	61.55%
	Total 110		110	100.00%

Table 5 shows the posts held by the select respondents employed in the BHEL. In the total select respondents of this study, the 61.55% of the respondents are working as the HR executives; the 19.23%, the Managers; the 11.53%, the top management of the HR department; the 7.69%, Sr. managers of the HR department in the BHEL.

Effects of HRIS on HR Function: The following Table 6 shows the effects of HRIS on HR functions in the BHEL

Table 6: Effects of HRIS on HR Function

S.No	HR Function	Highly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Highly Disagree
1	Gathers, stores and analyses the information	71.15%	28.85%	-----	-----
2	Enhances organisational performance	21.15%	78.85%	-----	-----
3	Increases administrative efficiency	21.15%	78.85%	-----	-----
4	Benefits administration work	33.60%	61.15%	15.25%	-----
5	Makes work easier	15.38%	84.62%	-----	-----
6	Addresses the complexities associated with people management	15.25%	66.40%	18.35%	-----
7	Improves the work environment	50.00%	50.00%	-----	-----
8	Helps talent management	11.65%	88.35%	-----	-----
9	Increases the quality of work	10.25%	89.75%	-----	-----
10	Helps in decision making	50.00%	50.00%	-----	-----

Table 6 shows the effects of the HRIS on the HR function. The 71.15% of the respondents highly agrees that the HRIS helps the HR department gather, store, and analyse the information on the HR activities. With the two different statements, the 78.85% of the respondents agrees that the HRIS increases the administrative efficiency in the HR department and enhancing the organizational performance as well; the 61.15%, giving the benefits of administration; the 84.62%, making the work easier; the 66.40%, addressing the complexities associated with the people of the management; the 88.35%, helping the talent management and the 89.75%, increasing the work quality. The 50% of the respondents highly agrees with the two different statements that the HRIS improves the work environment and helping the HR department to undertake the decision-making process. Finally, the researcher has concluded from the Table 6 that the HRIS implementation successfully in the organisation gives more positive effects on the HR functions.

Effectiveness of HRIS on HR functions: The following Table shows the effectiveness of the HRIS on the HR functions

Table 7: Effectiveness of HRIS on HR functions

S.No	HR Functions	Highly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Highly Disagree
1	Replaces manual processing	23.25%	65.10%	-----	11.65%
2	Gives strategic competencies	06.55%	79.25%	12.20%	-----

3	Reduces cost of HR	-----	100.00%	-----	-----
4	Aligns the needs with the operating system	19.10%	77.10%	03.80%	-----
5	Helps the staff planning	81.20%	18.80%	-----	-----
6	Identifies and retains HR talents	82.25%	17.75%	-----	-----
7	Helps in recruitment process	58.95%	23.50%	17.55	-----
8	Develops training modules	26.15%	73.85%	-----	-----
9	Keeps Record-absence management	28.10%	71.90%	-----	-----
10	Improves payroll system	09.15%	90.85%	-----	-----
11	Improves time and attendance	07.90%	92.10%	-----	-----
12	Improves performance appraisal system	09.25%	90.75%	-----	-----
13	Improves performance record	34.25%	62.35%	03.80%	-----
14	Improves scheduling system	22.65%	58.45%	19.90%	-----

Recently, many organizations have started implementing the HRIS as to the recruitment, the selection, the hiring, the job placement, the performance appraisals, the employee benefit analysis, the health, the safety, and the security. Table 7 clearly shows the effectiveness of the HRIS on the HR functions. Of the total select respondents of this study, the 82.25% of the respondents highly agrees that the HRIS helps identify and retaining the HR talents; the 81.20%, helping the staff planning and the 58.95%, supporting the recruitment process.

The 100% of the respondents highly agrees with the statement expressing that the HRIS reduces the cost of the HR; the 92.10%, enhancing the payroll system; the 90.75%, increasing the time and attendance; the 90.85%, improving the performance; the 79.25%, giving the strategic competitiveness 77.10%, aligning the needs with the operational system, the 73.85%, developing the training modules; the 65.10%, replacing the manuals processing; the 62.35, improving the performance record; and the 58.48%, alerting the scheduling system. The study has concluded that out of the 110 participants, the most (78.64%) agrees and a few (21.35%) highly agrees that the organisation can realize the value from the HRIS effectiveness.

Impact of HRIS on HR Activities: The following Table 8 shows the impact of the HRIS on the HR activities

Table 8: Impact of HRIS on HR activities

S.No	HR Activities	Highly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Highly Disagree
1	Develops structure of HR	26.90%	74.10%	-----	-----
2	Improves system of HR	26.80%	73.20%	-----	-----
3	Improves style of HR	-----	100.00%	-----	-----
4	Improves the skills and competencies of HR	19.90%	80.10%	-----	-----
5	Improves the area of HR activities	-----	100.00%	-----	-----
6	Takes stock of HR activities	-----	100.00%	-----	-----
7	changes the role of HR	-----	100.00%	-----	-----

Table 8 clearly shows the impact of the HRIS on the HR activities. The 100% of the respondents agrees with the four different statements that the HRIS improves the areas of HR activities, taking stock of HR activities, changing the role of the HR and improving the style of HR; the 80.10%, improving the skills and competencies of the HR; the 74.10%, developing the structure of the HR and the 73.20%, improving the system of the HR. This study shows that the impact of the HRIS brings about the development and making the HR Department more competent.

Summary and Conclusions:

The HRIS provides the information and guidance for the HR department operation and making this information readily available and useful for the managerial decision-making. The HRIS is able to acquire and track any kind of data, bringing about an improvement in the overall HR functions of the organization and being a powerful tool to change the HR Department activities in all organizations. This research paper shows that the HRIS is complicated and difficult to work. But, it helps align the HR practices with the organizational strategy. It identifies areas improving and keeping abreast with the current practices. It allows an organization to assess and evaluate any gaps or the potential risks. It increases the commitment of the HR professionals to the continuous improvement. It increases the efficiency of the HR function. It helps contribute to the potentials of the HR Department towards the organization. It develops the structure, the payroll, the time and attendance. It appraises the employees' performance. It recruits the workers, improving the training system, keeping the performance record, the employee self-service, the scheduling, and the absence management systems. It reduces the HR cost, increasing the motivation of the HR personnel. It analyses the problems and solving them smoothly. It develops the sound performance appraisal systems, the systematic job analysis and the smooth adoption of the changing mind-set. By making the HRIS a part of the organization, the HR Department can transform itself to be a strategic business.

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